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The Lost Legacy of a Development Perspective in IndiaJournal of **Social Sciences**

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Abstract:

The early rulers of independent India to consciously avoided extremes of any ideological moorings and tried to reconcile and accommodate different pulls and pressures. The state was sought to be arbiter and tool for achieving and attaining the goal of nation building and economic development. These factors placed India in a unique situation of having the socialistic pattern of social order to be its achievable goal with all its welfare orientation. In this context, the role played by Mahatma Gandhi, Jawaharlal Nehru and Dr. B. R. Ambedkar in designing and shaping of the Indian development perspective and more particularly the drafting of the Indian constitution by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar keeping those values in perspective, is worth mentioning in the neo-liberal era of fast changing global world order in which state has been made subservient to the market since the late 1980s. my paper tries to analyse the factors and influences that compelled the Indian State to be a social democratic state and its lost legacy in the overarching era of neoliberal globalized world order.

Keywords:

Socialist pattern of development, Neoliberalism, Nehru, Ambedkar and Gandhi

Introduction

The American led capitalist system which was the product of industrial revolution reached its zenith with colonialism and imperialism was held responsible for the ills of the world. The two world wars were fought. There was a lot of inequality within the countries and among the countries of capitalism. The capitalism enabled the capitalist class to appropriate the huge surplus that had been created after industrial revolution. The working class which Karl Marx called proletariat suffered with poverty and lived in precarious conditions. The capitalist system of production abetted the entrenched traditional social, economic and political structures to carry on the oppressive social order. Communism in Russia was seen as an antidote to end the oppression of the working class and domination of the traditional forces in the society. The communist ideology wanted to establish egalitarian social order by overthrowing the capitalist class and the state which was seen as a tool of oppression in the hands of capitalist class. But the communist state witnessed violence and showed severe autocratic and totalitarian tendencies.

Thus, the severe shortcomings of the communism in Russia and the capitalism in America were well understood by Indian intellectuals, consisting of people from different backgrounds ranging from underprivileged sections to feudal sections of the society under the umbrella of Indian National Congress of Gandhi who was spearheading the freedom struggle in India with the principles of Non-violence and Satyagraha with the cooperation from capitalists and the masses as well. Apart from this, the freedom struggle saw many contradictions. On the one hand there was large scale participation of the masses especially after the entry of Gandhiji, and on the other hand, initially and later it had been carried forward and led by elite sections of the society under the umbrella of same Indian National Congress. Even groups and organizations with different ideologies were forced to work for a long time under the leadership of Gandhi. Hindu Maha Sabha and Muslim league which later became active to achieve their own communal agendas had influenced

the course of freedom struggle and the policy making of independent India. The Republican Party of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar representing the interests and aspirations of the long oppressed untouchable caste people also had the influence on the shaping and making of the development agenda of post independent India.

All these factors forced the then early rulers of independent India to avoid extremes of any ideological moorings and tried to reconcile and accommodate different pulls and pressures. The state was sought to be arbiter and tool for achieving and attaining the goal of nation building and economic development. These factors placed India in a unique situation of having the socialistic pattern of social order to be its achievable goal with all its welfare orientation. In this context, the role played by Mahatma Gandhi, Jawaharlal Nehru and Dr. B. R. Ambedkar in designing and shaping of the Indian development perspective and more particularly the drafting of the Indian constitution by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar keeping those values in perspective, is worth mentioning in the neo-liberal era of fast changing global world order in which state has been made subservient to the market since the late 1980s.

Neo-liberalism since then has become the dominant development perspective. Neo-liberalism refers to the transformation of the state from a provider of public welfare to a promoter of market and competition (William Harvey, 2005). Neo-liberalism also means the application of market-based principles and techniques of evaluation to the state endorsed norms (William Davies, 2014). This era of neoliberalism has been inconsistent with the long-held development perspective rooted in Indian Freedom struggle, constitutional and the intellectual and philosophical thinking of Gandhi, Nehru and Ambedkar.

Jawaharlal Nehru and the Social Democracy

Jawaharlal Nehru who was chosen by Gandhi became the first Prime Minister of independent India. Even before independence, a faction led by Subhas Chandra Bose and Nehru himself in the Indian National Congress was influenced by the thought and practice of USSR. However, after becoming Prime Minister, Nehru had to work with rightist ideologues like Rajendra Prasad and Vallabai Patel and also with some industrialists who not only participated in the Freedom struggle but also prepared the Bombay Plan.

Although Jawaharlal Nehru did not officially accept the plan, "the Nehruvian era witnessed the implementation of the Bombay Plan; a substantially interventionist state and an economy with a sizeable public sector." (Ananth, V. Krishna, 2005). Its perceived influence has given it iconic status, and "it is no exaggeration to say that the Bombay Plan has come to occupy something of a mythic position in Indian historiography. There is scarcely a study of post-war Indian economic history that does not point to it as an indicator of the developmental and nationalistic aspiration of the domestic capitalist class (Chibber, Vivek, 2003).

Apart from these historical incidents and compulsions, Nehru's personality itself was very much accommodative. He perceived secularism, nationalism, and socialism from the point of view of democracy which, according to him, is based on the principles of equality, justice and fraternity. For equal distribution, which was the central aim of his socialism project, there need to be very high production on massive scale for which the state had to intervene. Based on constitutional values of equality, justice and fraternity, he felt nation building and economic development have to be achieved through active state intervention.

Therefore, Nehru emphasized on rapid industrialization with the development of heavy industry, high investment in science and technology, the training of a large technical and scientific cadre, which were seen as necessary instruments for achieving independent economic development. He wanted the state to be a principal entrepreneur and all its citizens its equal shareholders. Nehru's economics of state intervention and investment were conceived at a time when the transfers of capital and technology that were important to India were not easily forthcoming from the developed world and the private sector.

His ideology of social democracy aims at political, economic and social equality. For him, political equality implies universal adult franchise, legislatures with a true representative character, freedom of the press and public opinion, political rights, constitutional safeguards. Nehru helped and endeavoured to create a country with enduring civic institutions, a strong and socially responsive judiciary, a committed civilian control of the army and overall egalitarianism and secularism.

Economic equality means nationalization of means of production, participation of workers in decision-making along with the management, granting of economic rights in all spheres, ceiling of property, progressive legislation on property rights, de-concentration of wealth, and state intervention to secure economic security and equality.

For him, social equality means the removal of social discrimination on the grounds of race, sex, gender and natural incapacities and equal opportunities to lead a happy life in the social sphere. It also includes elimination of poverty, provision of education and health, elimination of social stigma and inhuman activities, extension of voting rights to the underprivileged, equal participation of women without gender inequality.

Nehru's policies were credited with setting up India's infrastructure for scientific education, nuclear programme, space programme, the extensive Indian Railways network, and the pharmaceutical industry. It is to his credit that he did not abuse power and constantly attempted to deepen the democratic nature of institutions of the newly independent India with the intervention of the state in a big way.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and the State Socialism

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar who himself suffered humiliation from caste oppression looked at Indian society as structurally unequal on account of the caste system and he perceived that any reform aimed at establishing egalitarian order has to first address the question of caste-based inequality. He thought that without destroying the caste system, it was not possible to bring about a socialist revolution in India. Instead of socialist revolution which involves violence and dictatorship, he preferred Fabian socialism which aims at establishing socialist order through evolutionary reformation of the established order. He criticized the communists for ignoring caste and religion in India. He also emphasized the role of the state, which communists wanted to abolish ultimately to establish stateless and classless society, to bring about the transformation of the society. He was for 'state socialism'.

As a sole representative of the Dalits, he presented a memorandum called 'States and Minorities' on behalf of the Scheduled Caste Federation before the constituent assembly. In the memorandum, he drew up an elaborate plan of action for the state to run key industries and also to acquire agricultural land to be leased out to the farming collective of the villages (Anand Teltumbde, 2018). Thus, he visualized and

sought active state intervention for bringing about transformation of Indian society based on the values of equality, liberty and justice.

Mahatma Gandhi and the Gram Swarajya

The first half of the twentieth century of Indian history and emergence of Indian welfare state was very much influenced by the precept and practice of Gandhi. His non-violent strategies motivated the common people to participate in the freedom struggle. From extreme left to rightist ideologues of all groups were compelled to work under his leadership.

Non-violence, Truth and Satyagraha were the fundamental principles on which he wanted to transform the Indian society while liberating it from the clutches of the British colonial rule. He dreamt of Independent India to be based on Gram Swarajya, that is, a self-reliant village, as more than 80 per cent of Indians then live in villages. He considered villages to be primary units of decentralization which, he felt, enables wider participation of the people making representative democracy a participatory democracy. Thus, his development approach was mainly rested in self-reliant villages. He was deeply sceptical about the concentration of power in a centralized state (James Manor,2010).

He opposed urban based big industrialization. He felt that installation of large-scale machinery would result in large scale retrenchment of the workers. The urban areas would become the breeding grounds for violence, consumer culture and pollution. Panchayat Raj system, development of agriculture and animal husbandry, village based small scale and cottage industries were enshrined in the constitution as directive principles of state policy. Apart from these, educational development of SCs and STs and other backward classes, abolition of intoxicants, abolition of cow slaughter were also included.

Thus, Gandhi, Nehru and Ambedkar, though they were holding different approaches for the development of Independent India, influenced the emergence of Indian welfare state after independence. Gandhi was for village development; Nehru was for big industrial development and Ambedkar for social equality to be achieved through socialist state. The underlying commonality of all these three great personalities was liberal approach which enabled India to be a welfare state. These three personalities had greatly influenced the shaping of the Indian development perspective and accordingly the constitution with focus on Fundamental rights and the Directive Principles as well was drafted under the chairmanship of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar. But after the reforms during the globalised world since 1980s, the emphasis has been on unfettering capitalism. The transition is from socialistic pattern of development to capitalistic pattern of development where welfare expenditure is looked down leading to cut in subsidized goods and services to the poor and peasant farmers. As the public institutions are being crippled, private sector participation with all the state support would get legitimized further benefitting the later with huge transfer of public resources. All these have become normalized practices of neo-liberalism, severely affecting the constitutionally legitimized Indian welfare state in general and social sectors in particular with all the traditional public institutions on which the poor depend are being subject to market-based principles and evaluation strategies of neo-liberal agenda of development.

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